

Effect of Different Groups on Cyclopentadienyl Ring on the Stability of Titanium-Cyclopentadienyl Bond

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Reactions of $ABTiCl_3$ (A=cyclopentadienyl and B=methylcyclopentadienyl or indenyl) with sodium salts of dithiocarbamic acids, $Na(S_2CNRR')$ ($R=R'=CH_3$, C_6H_5 , $i-C_3H_7$; or $R=CH_3$ and $R'=C_6H_5$) have been carried out in the molar ratio of 1 : 3. It was found that in case of $[(\eta^5-C_5H_5)(\eta^5-CH_2C_5H_4)]TiCl_3$, the cyclopentadienyl ring was knocked off resulting in the formation of $(\eta^5-CH_2C_5H_4)Ti(S_2CNRR')_3$, whereas, in case of $[(\eta^5-C_5H_5)(\eta^5-C_6H_7)]TiCl_3$, the indenyl ring was knocked off resulting in the formation of $(\eta^5-C_5H_5)Ti(S_2CNRR')_3$. A suitable explanation for this observation has been proposed.

SUBSTITUTION on Cp ring affects the stability of titanium-cyclopentadienyl bond i.e., in case of $(\eta^5-C_5H_5)TiCl_3$, cyclopentadienyl ring is lost by alkaline hydrolysis, whereas $[(\eta^5-CH_2C_5H_4)]TiCl_3$ is converted only to $[(\eta^5-(CH_2)_5C_5)Ti(OH)]_3$ ¹. In the other case, unlike $(\eta^5-Cp)_2Ti(CH_3)_2$, the yellow pentane solutions of $[(\eta^5-(CH_2)_5C_5)_2Ti(CH_3)_2]$ were found to show no reactivity towards H_2 even at 100 atm pressure². Recently, it has been established that in the reaction of $(\eta^5-C_5H_5)_2MCl_2$ or $(\eta^5-CH_2C_5H_4)_2MCl_2$, (M=Ti, Zr or Hf), with sodium dithiocarbamates in the ratio of 1 : 3, one cyclopentadienyl or methylcyclopentadienyl ring is knocked off resulting in the formation of $(\eta^5-C_5H_5)M(DTC)_3$ or $(\eta^5-CH_2C_5H_4)M(DTC)_3$ ^{1,2}.

In the present communication reactions of $ABTiCl_3$, [A= $\eta^5-C_5H_5$, B= $\eta^5-CH_2C_5H_4$ or $\eta^5-C_6H_7$ (indenyl)], with $Na(S_2CNRR')$, ($R=R'=CH_3$, C_6H_5 , $i-C_3H_7$; or $R=CH_3$, $R'=C_6H_5$), have been studied with a view to ascertain the effect of the different groups present on cyclopentadienyl ring on the stability of titanium-cyclopentadienyl bond. In the case of $[(\eta^5-C_5H_5)(\eta^5-CH_2C_5H_4)]TiCl_3$, cyclopentadienyl ring is knocked off indicating that the $-CH_2$ group present on the cyclopentadienyl ring imparts stability to titanium-cyclopentadienyl bond, whereas in the case of $[(\eta^5-C_5H_5)(\eta^5-C_6H_7)]TiCl_3$, indenyl ring is knocked off thereby indicating that the presence of phenyl ring fused to cyclopentadienyl ring (in indenyl) makes the titanium-cyclopentadienyl bond fragile.

Experimental

Reagents and general techniques: $[(\eta^5-C_5H_5)(\eta^5-CH_2C_5H_4)]TiCl_3$ was prepared by the reaction of $\eta^5-CpTiCl_3$ and $(\eta^5-CH_2C_5H_4)Ti$ (I) in 1 : 1 molar ratio in THF. $[(\eta^5-C_5H_5)(\eta^5-C_6H_7)]TiCl_3$ was prepared by the reaction of $\eta^5-CpTiCl_3$ and sodium indenide in 1 : 1 molar ratio in $THF^{1,3}$. Sodium salts of dithiocarbamic acids were prepared

as described by Kloppling and Kerk^{1,4} and dried before use. All the organic solvents used were predried and well purified.

Preparation of the complexes :

[A] Reaction of sodium salt of *N,N*-dimethyl-dithiocarbamic acid on $[(\eta^5-C_5H_5)(\eta^5-CH_2C_5H_4)]TiCl_3$: $[(\eta^5-C_5H_5)(\eta^5-CH_2C_5H_4)]TiCl_3$ (0.2630 g ; 0.001 mole) was refluxed with $Na[S_2CN(CH_3)_2]$ (0.4290 g ; 0.003 mole) in CH_2Cl_2 (50 ml) for 10 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and filtered. The volume of the filtrate was reduced to ~10 ml in *vacuo* and petroleum ether (60-80°) was added dropwise to precipitate the complex. The precipitate was filtered, dried and recrystallized from 1 : 1 mixture of dichloromethane and petroleum ether to isolate the yellow orange product, $(\eta^5-CH_2C_5H_4)Ti[S_2CN(CH_3)_2]_3$ in >90% yield. Reactions of $[(\eta^5-C_5H_5)(\eta^5-CH_2C_5H_4)]TiCl_3$ with other dithiocarbamates, i.e., $Na(S_2CNRR')$, ($R=R'=C_6H_5$, $i-C_3H_7$; or $R=CH_3$, $R'=C_6H_5$), in 1 : 3 molar ratio were carried out in similar manner and yielded corresponding mono(methylcyclopentadienyl) trisdithiocarbamatotitanium (IV) complexes in >90% yield.

[B] Reaction of sodium salt of *N,N*-disubstituted dithiocarbamic acid on $[(\eta^5-C_5H_5)(\eta^5-C_6H_7)]TiCl_3$: Reactions of $[(\eta^5-C_5H_5)(\eta^5-C_6H_7)]TiCl_3$ with $Na(S_2CNRR')$, ($R=R'=CH_3$, C_6H_5 , $i-C_3H_7$; or $R=CH_3$, $R'=C_6H_5$), in 1 : 3 molar ratio were also carried out in the manner as described in [A] to yield the respective mono(cyclopentadienyl) trisdithiocarbamatotitanium(IV) complexes in >90% yield.

Physico-chemical measurements : The ir spectra in the region 4000-250 cm^{-1} were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 621 grating spectrophotometer. The ¹H nmr spectra were recorded at ambient temperature ~30° in $CDCl_3$ on a Varian A-60 NMR spectrometer at a sweep width of 500 Hz using TMS as an internal standard. Molecular weight of

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA FOR $(\eta^5\text{-CH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)\text{Ti}(\text{S}_2\text{CNRR}')_2$ AND $(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{S}_2\text{CNRR}')_2$

Complex	Molar conductivity $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mole}^{-1}$	Concentration mM	Molecular weight Found (Calcd.)	Analysis% Found (Calcd.)				m.p. and colour
				C	H	N	Ti	
$(\eta^5\text{-CH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)\text{Ti}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{CH}_3)_2]_2$	0.22	0.5	490 (487)	40.1 (37.0)	5.2 (5.1)	8.5 (8.6)	9.8 (9.9)	160° Yellow
$(\eta^5\text{-CH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)\text{Ti}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2]_2$	0.20	0.5	565 (571)	43.8 (44.1)	6.4 (6.5)	7.2 (7.3)	8.1 (8.4)	153° Yellow
$(\eta^5\text{-CH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)\text{Ti}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(i\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7)_2]_2$	0.23	0.4	660 (655)	48.9 (49.5)	7.6 (7.5)	6.2 (6.4)	7.4 (7.3)	170° Yellow orange
$(\eta^5\text{-CH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)\text{Ti}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{CH}_3)(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)]_2$	0.25	0.5	690 (673)	54.2 (53.5)	4.5 (4.6)	6.5 (6.2)	7.3 (7.1)	90° Orange yellow
$(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{CH}_3)_2]_2$	0.22	0.5	431 (473)	35.2 (35.5)	4.7 (4.86)	8.7 (8.88)	10.3 (10.15)	240° Yellow orange
$(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2]_2$	0.21	0.5	512 (557)	43.2 (43.09)	6.1 (6.28)	7.2 (7.54)	8.3 (8.62)	250° Yellow orange
$(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(i\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7)_2]_2$	0.21	0.5	655 (641)	49.1 (48.7)	7.4 (7.3)	6.7 (6.5)	7.3 (7.5)	149° Orange yellow
$(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{CH}_3)(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)]_2$	0.20	0.5	668 (659)	53.5 (52.8)	4.3 (4.4)	6.5 (6.37)	7.4 (7.28)	101° Orange

TABLE 2—PROTON CHEMICAL SHIFT (τ VALUES IN ppm) AT $\sim 30^\circ$ IN CDCl_3

Complex	$\text{CH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4$ or C_5H_5 ring protons	CH_2 protons of $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4$	$(\text{S}_2\text{CNRR}')_2$ protons			$-\text{CH}_3$ protons
			$-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ protons	$\rightarrow\text{CH}$ protons	$-\text{CH}_3$ protons	
$(\eta^5\text{-CH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)\text{Ti}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{CH}_3)_2]_2$	4.43(t), 4.00(t)	7.75	—	—	—	6.76(d) (5 : 1)
$(\eta^5\text{-CH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)\text{Ti}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2]_2$	4.53(t), 4.1(t)	7.80	—	—	6.325(q)	8.33(t)
$(\eta^5\text{-CH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)\text{Ti}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(i\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7)_2]_2$	4.48(t), 4.05(t)	7.77	—	5.28(m)	—	A 8.66(d) (2 : 1) B 8.61(d) (2 : 1)
$(\eta^5\text{-CH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)\text{Ti}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{CH}_3)(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)]_2$	4.55(t), 4.17(t)	7.85	2.89(d) (2 : 1)	—	—	6.51(d) (2 : 1) 6.76(d) (5 : 1) 8.53(t)
$(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{CH}_3)_2]_2$	4.1	—	—	—	—	6.76(d) (5 : 1) 8.53(t)
$(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2]_2$	3.78	—	—	—	6.975(q)	8.53(t)
$(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(i\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7)_2]_2$	4.05	—	—	5.52(m)	—	A 8.64(d) (2 : 1) B 8.57(d) (2 : 1)
$(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}[\text{S}_2\text{CN}(\text{CH}_3)(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)]_2$	3.73	—	2.59(d) (2 : 1)	—	—	7.975(d) (2 : 1)

m = multiplet, q = quartet, t = triplet, d = doublet; A and B are the two doublets of equal intensity.

the complexes were determined on Gallenkamp ebullioscope in benzene and conductivity measurements were carried out in nitrobenzene using Elico CM82T conductivity bridge.

Results and Discussion

The reactions of $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\eta^5\text{-CH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)]\text{TiCl}_2$ or $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)]\text{TiCl}_2$ with $\text{Na}(\text{S}_2\text{CNRR}')$ ($\text{R}=\text{R}'=\text{CH}_3$, C_6H_5 , $i\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7$; or $\text{R}=\text{CH}_3$ and $\text{R}'=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) in 1 : 3 molar ratio have been studied in nonaqueous medium. These reactions may be represented as :

These complexes are yellow orange to orange in colour and are insoluble in H_2O and petroleum ether but are highly soluble in CHCl_3 , CH_2Cl_2 , C_6H_6 , CS_2 , CH_3COCH_3 and THF. They are thermally stable but slowly hydrolyse on exposure to moist air. The conductivity measurements in nitrobenzene and molecular weight determinations in benzene indicate that the complexes are non-electrolytic monomers. Physical data for these complexes are given in Table 1. These complexes have also been prepared previously by the reaction of $(\eta^5\text{-CH}_2\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)_2\text{TiCl}_2$ or $(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{TiCl}_2$ and $\text{Na}(\text{S}_2\text{CNRR}')^{-10}$.

Infrared spectra : The ir spectrum of each of these complexes shows only one $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ at $\sim 1505\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and only one $\nu\text{C}=\text{S}$ at $\sim 1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The pentahapto cyclopentadienyl ring in the complexes $(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Ti}(\text{S}_2\text{CNRR}')_2$ is identified by the characteristic ir bands viz., C-H stretching at $\sim 2925\text{ cm}^{-1}$,

C-C stretching at $\sim 1430\text{ cm}^{-1}$, symmetric ring breathing at $\sim 1120\text{ cm}^{-1}$, C-H asymmetric in plane deformation at $\sim 1050\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and C-H out of plane deformation at $\sim 845, \sim 800\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The presence of pentahapto methylcyclopentadienyl ring in the complexes $(\eta^5\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)\text{Ti}(\text{S}_2\text{CNRR}')_2$ is identified by the characteristic ir bands viz., C-H stretching (ring) at $\sim 3100\text{ cm}^{-1}$, C-C stretching at $\sim 1435\text{ cm}^{-1}$, symmetrical ring breathing $\sim 1125\text{ cm}^{-1}$, C-H asymmetric in plane deformation at $\sim 1035\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and C-H out of plane deformation at $\sim 865, \sim 825\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The ir data for these complexes are similar to those already prepared⁶⁻¹⁰. Therefore, the dithiocarbamate ligands in these complexes are bidentate and a coordination number of 'seven' may be assigned to titanium as already discussed⁶⁻¹⁰.

¹H nmr spectra : The ¹H nmr data for these complexes are given in Table 2 and are similar to those already reported⁶⁻¹⁰. Therefore, these complexes are stereochemically rigid heptacoordinate chelates which assume different geometries⁶⁻¹⁰.

Effect of the different groups present on the cyclopentadienyl ring on the stability of titanium-cyclopentadienyl ring : The reactions of $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5)(\eta^5\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)]\text{TiCl}_2$ or $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5)(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)]\text{TiCl}_2$ with sodium salts of N,N-disubstituted dithiocarbamic acids in 1 : 3 molar ratio yield trisdithiocarbamate complexes and one ring out of the two attached to titanium is knocked off. Naturally, the one having weaker titanium ring bond will be knocked off leaving the other ring having comparatively stronger bond with titanium.

In the case of the reaction of $(\eta^5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5)(\eta^5\text{-CH}_3\text{-C}_5\text{H}_4)\text{TiCl}_2$ with sodium dithiocarbamate, the cyclopentadienyl ring is knocked off. It clearly indicates that $(\eta^5\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)\text{-Ti}$ bond is stronger than $(\eta^5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5)\text{-Ti}$ bond. In fact, the electron releasing property of the methyl group present on the cyclopentadienyl ring in methylcyclopentadienyl group increases the electron density in the ring, imparting thereby additional stability to the titanium-methylcyclopentadienyl bond. Thus, as compared to titanium-methylcyclopentadienyl bond, titanium-cyclopentadienyl bond becomes relatively fragile and can be knocked off by dithiocarbamate ligand.

On the other hand in the case of the reaction of $(\eta^5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5)(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)\text{TiCl}_2$ with sodium dithiocarbamates, the indenyl ring is knocked off. It indicates

that $(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)\text{-Ti}$ bond is weaker than $(\eta^5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5)\text{-Ti}$ bond. In fact the electron withdrawing property of C_6H_5 ring fused to cyclopentadienyl ring (in indenyl ring) decreases the electron density of the cyclopentadienyl ring of the indenyl group. Thus, $(\eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7)\text{-Ti}$ bond becomes weaker as compared to $(\eta^5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5)\text{-Ti}$ bond. Therefore, preferential removal of indenyl ring by dithiocarbamate ligand takes place during the formation of trisdithiocarbamate complexes.

It is, therefore, concluded that the electron releasing groups present on cyclopentadienyl ring increases the stability of titanium-cyclopentadienyl bond whereas the presence of electron withdrawing groups on cyclopentadienyl ring makes the titanium-cyclopentadienyl bond fragile and exchangeable. The order of stability is $\eta^5\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{-Ti} > \eta^5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-Ti} > \eta^5\text{-C}_9\text{H}_7\text{-Ti}$. During the reaction with DTC, one ring always remains attached with titanium. The fact has been ascertained through ¹H nmr spectra of the resultant products.

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